

ISic0094

I.Sicily inscription 0094

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. M(arco) · Cestio · P(ubli) · f(ilio) · Cla(udia)
2. primo · pilo · praef(ecto)
3. fabrum · trib(uno) · mil(itum)
4. IIvir(o) · ex · d(ecreto) · d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285286

EDR 127507

EDCS 22100049

Bibliography

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